

Digitalization of public civil services: practical experience of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The article reviews and analyzes international experience of forming government and digital economy, provides information about model of maturity and readiness of countries to e-government. The article also considers the main principles of development of e-government in Uzbekistan and the practical mechanisms for implementation. In the end, the article provides short result of practical implementation.*

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The international community pays great attention to the integration process of information and communication technologies into public administration, the interaction of the government bodies with the population and business entities, the protection of their rights and interests, and the creation of additional opportunities and amenities. One of the widely used mechanisms for assessing the effectiveness of measures of implementation is to build the country's short-term and long-term strategic objectives on the basis of an assessment of the maturity of the e-Government system.

The analysis of international experience (Korea, Great Britain, Estonia, Russia and Singapore) shows that for the comprehensive, effective development of e-government, the systematic solution of the tasks with the use of ICT opportunities, as well as the qualitative realization of the tasks to form the strategic goals of the countries, comprehensive programs are being developed and implemented, which include a strategy for the introduction and development of ICT into the public administration system.

The e-government strategy of the Republic of Korea contributed to over 409 projects which were implemented by small and medium-sized enterprises. Integration of information systems of e-government has been carried out, up to 40% of regulation documents in the field of public administration and public service have been adopted, open access to data necessary for interaction with the state has been provided (more than 300 thousand downloads of source code of the unified standardized platform of e-government based on software with open architecture have been carried out).

Over the years, the Republic of Korea has maintained its position as Asia's leader and has repeatedly been recognized as the world leader in the development of e-government. The analysis showed that the example of building an e-government architecture based on a clear delineation of information systems by domain, as in the Republic of Korea, is one of the best approaches.

The e-government architecture of the Republic of Korea consists of a citizen identification system, a single data exchange platform, information resources, information systems and databases in various areas of social and economic development of the country and the life of the population.

The UK is currently in rapid development of e-government, which allows the country to be among the 10 leading countries in the UN Rating since 2003.

In April 2012, the State Digital Service under the Cabinet of Ministers of Great Britain officially announced the launch of the gov.uk, a government portal based on the principle of a single window, providing the opportunity to obtain information and public services.

The activities implemented by the UK Government have reduced costs and improved the efficiency of public ICT systems, solved a number of socio-economic problems by centralizing control, creating equal opportunities for open source software, creating a state-wide "app store," encouraging regular reporting by ministers and senior government officials on the progress of ICT projects and programmes.

Estonia is recognized to be as the most advanced digital society, has become one of the countries that has created an effective, safe and transparent e-government ecosystem. The phased introduction and development of Estonia's e-government began 25 years ago, when there were no digital data on citizens and the population did not have access to the Internet. Despite this, by 1997 97% of schools had introduced ICT into their activities, in 2000, most meetings of government organizations were held without paper costs. Soon, in 2002, the government built a free Wi-Fi network that covered most regions of country. The X-Road project, as the basis of Estonia's e-government, provides electronic interaction not only between public authorities, but also between private information systems of electronic service to more than 1000 Estonian organizations and the provision of 99% of public services in electronic form.

In the Russian Federation, the State programme "Information Society" was developed to create effective system for the use of information technologies. The state program covers all sectors and spheres of activity to increase transparency and manageability, ensure stability and competitiveness of the economy as a whole. The strategy for the development of the information society is aimed at working in the areas of creation of e-government, overcoming digital inequality, development of new communication technologies.

The E-Government Improvement Programme in Singapore is aimed at the development of promising information technologies, the creation of high-speed data transmission networks infrastructure in the country, the expansion of the use of the Internet, the development of electronic commerce, which directly contributes to the reduction of tariffs for all types of communication. It is also an undeniable advantage of Singapore's projects to

promote ICT projects through public-private partnerships.

As the review shows, the international community is paying particular attention to the integration of information and communication technologies into public administration, and one of the widely used tools for measuring the effectiveness of measures is to build the country's short- and long-term strategic objectives by assessing the maturity of e-government.

The e-government maturity model is a set of stages (from basic to advanced) that determine the level of e-government development based on certain characteristics and criteria. To date, there are more than 30 e-government maturity models. The most popular, recognized advanced countries of the world and combining the most important characteristics of 25 maturity models, was the "Gartner model."

According to the "Gartner model," the maturity level of e-government is divided into 5 stages:

The first stage – initial e-government, an e-government that forms the basic elements of e-government, the main goal of public policy is to introduce information and communication technologies into the public administration system, to create official websites of public authorities, to translate public services into electronic form;

The second stage – developing "open," an open government, in which the policy of the State is aimed at implementing the principle of providing public services "one window," creating platforms of electronic interaction of the State with the population and business entities, ensuring openness and transparency of the activities of State bodies;

The third stage – defined "data-centric," an integrated government, in which the country implements measures for the unconditional implementation of a unified technological approach in the introduction and development of information systems and resources of state bodies, provides centralized storage, processing and exchange of data, uses agreed, complementary and unified methods and approaches of interaction of e-government participants;

The fourth stage is managed "fully digital," a digital government in which information and communication technologies are applied as an integral part of the country's policy of modernizing the government to achieve the country's strategic goals by creating a digital ecosystem made up of government actors, non-governmental organizations, businesses, public associations and individuals that supports production and access to data, services and content through interaction with the government;

The fifth stage is optimizing "smart," a smart government characterized by complete automation and application of the principle of proactive activity in the interaction of the state with the population and business entities, interdepartmental cooperation of state bodies, ensuring the implementation of measures for the development of information and communication technologies in the system of state power and management on the basis of partnership relations between all participants of digital society.

E-government of the Republic of Uzbekistan ensures the provision of public services on the principle of "one

window," the implementation of open dialogue between the State and the population and business entities, through information and communication technologies, the establishment of mechanisms to ensure effective electronic participation and interaction between citizens and State bodies, and the gradual integration of information systems of State bodies for the organization of inter-agency electronic interaction in real time. These factors indicate that the electronic Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has reached the second stage of maturity of the electronic Government according to the "Gartner model."

However, a critical analysis of the current situation of e-government development points at the urgent need to remove barriers and barriers to the effective deployment of information and communications technologies, including:

First, insufficient technical infrastructure of e-government, including existing gaps in ensuring a common technological approach in the implementation and development of information systems, information resources and databases of public authorities;

Second, the bureaucracy and complexity of procedures for the provision of public services, the permitted cases of requests from the population and business entities for data and information available to public authorities;

Third, the lack of openness of the activities of State bodies and the manifestation of elements of information closure prevent the establishment of effective dialogue and interaction between State bodies and the population and business entities in the introduction of information and communication technologies in all spheres of development of the country;

Fourth, the remaining challenges and weaknesses in information security;

Fifth, lack of attention to the modern information and communication technologies aimed at the development of e-commerce, innovative technologies, including through research and public-private partnerships;

Sixth, the lack of an effective system of digital literacy, training, retraining and skills development in e-government, enabling continuous acquisition of information and communication technology skills at all levels.

Priority areas for further development of the Electronic Government system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2025 are:

- Development of the technical infrastructure of the E-government system is achieved with help of innovative technologies;

- The development of human capital and the improvement of soft skills;

- Digital transformation of public services;

- Ensuring the openness and transparency of the activities of State bodies and increasing the level of electronic participation of the population;

- Ensuring information security, protection of information resources and systems;

- development of an innovative ecosystem.

Digital transformation of public services requires first and foremost adherence to the following fundamental measures:

Implementation of the agreed unified state policy and the unified technological approach in the introduction, provision and further improvement of public services;

Development and implementation of the principle of proactive provision of electronic public services, in which the State body will inform citizens about the public services to which they are entitled on the basis of information available in information systems and resources;

Reform of the system of introduction of electronic public services with priority of comprehensive and qualitative analysis of the organization of works, providing for fundamental optimization of the procedure of their provision taking into account automation and public opinion;

Ensuring multichannel, flexible, convenient, transparent and secure methods of providing public services aimed at prioritizing the interests and convenience of the population and business entities, as well as access to public services anywhere, at any time and from any device.

Organization of systematic work to raise awareness of citizens and their interest in using the opportunities of information and communication technologies and remote receipt of public services.

Introduction of mechanisms that exclude excessive bureaucracy, the need to appeal to specific departments

and officials, excessive time spent by the applicant in the provision of public services.

Abovementioned mechanism allows to country to reach next results:

Obtaining services electronically, preferably for users, and fully meeting the needs of the population and business entities;

Creating an enabling environment for doing business through open legislative initiatives;

Strengthening trust relations between the population, business entities and public authorities in cooperation within the framework of e-government;

Ensuring information security of informatization facilities, strengthening safe interaction between citizens and the State;

Ensuring the effective functioning of an education system focused on digital literacy and adaptability to change in an era of accelerated adoption of information and communications technologies;

Improving the effectiveness of public authorities by involving the public in decisions to improve public administration;

Developing and strengthening human capital through the training and retraining of public servants and the population, including the unemployed, with the required digital skills.

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